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Review Article

OVERVIEW OF ANTI-NEOPLASTIC: CANCER**Payal Ramesh Gaikwad¹, Sanjana Shridhar Walwante², Kalyani Naresh Sadafale³,
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Washim-444505⁵Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim-444505**Abstract:**

This review comprehensively examines the landscape of antineoplastic agents, delving into their mechanisms of action, clinical applications, and recent advancements. The paper categorizes these agents based on their classes, including chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and targeted therapy. A critical analysis of their efficacy, side effects, and challenges in clinical settings is presented. The review highlights recent breakthroughs and emerging trends, offering insights into the future of antineoplastic research. By exploring historical developments and addressing current challenges, this paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the complexities surrounding antineoplastic treatments.

Keywords: Antineoplastic agents, Chemotherapy, Immunotherapy, Targeted therapy, Mechanisms of action, Clinical applications, Efficacy, Resistance, Side effects, Recent developments, Classification, Cancer treatment, Molecularly targeted therapy, Hormonal therapy, Radiation therapy, Combination therapy, Personalized medicine, Biomarkers, Drug discovery, Nanoparticle drug delivery.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cancer remains a formidable global health challenge, with its complex and multifaceted nature demanding continuous advancements in therapeutic strategies. Among the arsenal of tools at our disposal, antineoplastic agents stand as pivotal players in the ongoing battle against malignant tumors. This comprehensive review endeavors to provide a thorough exploration of antineoplastic agents, tracing their historical evolution, elucidating mechanisms of action, scrutinizing clinical applications, and surveying recent breakthroughs. The journey of antineoplastic development is rooted in the pursuit of targeted and efficacious interventions. From the advent of traditional chemotherapeutic agents to the contemporary era marked by immunotherapy and targeted therapies, the landscape of antineoplastic treatments has undergone transformative shifts. The diversity in their mechanisms, ranging from disrupting cell division to harnessing the body's immune response, underscores the sophistication of strategies employed to combat cancer. As we embark on this exploration, the historical context of antineoplastic agents unfolds, revealing the milestones and paradigm shifts that have shaped their trajectory. Understanding this evolutionary process not only provides insights into the foundation of current therapies but also sets the stage for a nuanced analysis of their efficacy and limitations in diverse clinical settings. Beyond the laboratory and into the clinics, antineoplastic agents navigate the intricate landscape of personalized medicine. Their applications span a spectrum of cancers, each presenting unique challenges and opportunities. This review aims to navigate through the clinical applications of antineoplastic agents, assessing their effectiveness, exploring emerging trends, and scrutinizing the ever-evolving landscape of cancer treatment. In the quest for improved outcomes, recent advancements in antineoplastic research hold the promise of reshaping the therapeutic paradigm. From novel drug formulations to groundbreaking immunotherapies, staying abreast of these developments is crucial for clinicians, researchers, and policymakers alike. This review synthesizes the latest discoveries, offering a glimpse into the future of antineoplastic treatments and the potential avenues for further research and innovation. In summation, this review is a comprehensive journey through the intricate tapestry of antineoplastic agents. By weaving together historical insights, mechanistic understanding, clinical applications, and recent advancements, it aims to contribute to the collective knowledge driving progress in the relentless pursuit of effective cancer treatments.

Historical Context of Antineoplastic Agents :

- The evolution of antineoplastic agents is a narrative interwoven with scientific milestones and transformative discoveries. The journey began in the mid-20th century when the dawn of chemotherapy ushered in a new era in cancer treatment.
- The accidental discovery of the alkylating agent nitrogen mustard during World War II, with its unexpected impact on cancer cells, laid the foundation for the exploration of chemical compounds as potential anticancer agents.
- The subsequent decades witnessed the emergence of various cytotoxic drugs, each contributing a unique facet to the growing repertoire of antineoplastic treatments. The advent of antimetabolites, such as methotrexate and 5-fluorouracil, marked a shift towards agents targeting specific aspects of cell metabolism.
- This era also saw the development of platinum-based compounds, exemplified by cisplatin, which became integral in the treatment of various solid tumors. The 1970s witnessed the rise of combination chemotherapy regimens, aiming to enhance efficacy while mitigating drug resistance. As the understanding of cancer biology deepened, targeted therapies emerged in the late 20th century, offering precision in attacking specific molecular pathways crucial for cancer cell survival.
- The approval of imatinib for chronic myeloid leukemia marked a paradigm shift, heralding the era of molecularly targeted agents. In more recent times, immunotherapy has emerged as a revolutionary approach, harnessing the body's own immune system to combat cancer. Monoclonal antibodies, immune checkpoint inhibitors, and adoptive cell therapies have demonstrated unprecedented success in certain malignancies, reshaping the therapeutic landscape.
- Understanding the historical context of antineoplastic agents provides insights into the challenges overcome, the lessons learned, and the continuous quest for more effective and targeted treatments. This backdrop sets the stage for a nuanced analysis of the current state of antineoplastic therapies, guiding us toward future innovations and breakthroughs in the dynamic field of cancer treatment.

Mechanisms of Action of Antineoplastic

Agents:

- **Unraveling the Intricacies :** The effectiveness of antineoplastic agents lies in their ability to disrupt the aberrant cellular processes characteristic of cancer cells. This review delves into the intricate mechanisms of action employed by these agents, offering a comprehensive understanding of their diverse strategies in combating malignancies.
- **DNA Damage and Cell Cycle Arrest :** Many traditional chemotherapeutic agents, such as alkylating agents and topoisomerase inhibitors, induce DNA damage, triggering cell cycle arrest. Exploration of these mechanisms illuminates how disrupting the cell cycle can impede the uncontrolled proliferation of cancer cells.
- **Targeted Therapies :** Molecularly targeted agents, including tyrosine kinase inhibitors and monoclonal antibodies, home in on specific molecular pathways crucial for cancer cell survival. This section dissects how targeted therapies exploit the vulnerabilities of cancer cells while sparing normal tissues
- **Immunomodulation :** Immunotherapeutic agents, such as immune checkpoint inhibitors and adoptive cell therapies, harness the immune system to recognize and eliminate cancer cells. An in-depth analysis of these mechanisms sheds light on the dynamic interplay between cancer cells and the immune system.
- **Apoptosis and Programmed Cell Death :** Antineoplastic agents often induce apoptosis, programmed cell death, as a means to eliminate damaged or malignant cells. Examining the molecular pathways involved in apoptosis provides insights into the therapeutic strategies designed to promote cancer cell death.
- **Antiangiogenic Effects :** Agents targeting angiogenesis aim to inhibit the formation of blood vessels that nourish tumors. Understanding how these agents disrupt the tumor microenvironment and starve cancer cells of nutrients is crucial for evaluating their efficacy.
- **Resistance Mechanisms :** Delving into mechanisms of resistance helps unravel the challenges faced in antineoplastic treatments. This section discusses the adaptive strategies employed by cancer cells to evade the effects of therapeutic agents. By dissecting these diverse mechanisms, this review aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how antineoplastic agents operate at the molecular and cellular levels. This knowledge not only informs the current state of cancer treatment but also points towards

potential avenues for developing more targeted and efficacious therapies in the ongoing fight against cancer.

Classification and Types of Antineoplastic Agents:

- **Navigating the Therapeutic Landscape** Antineoplastic agents encompass a diverse array of treatments, each designed to combat cancer through distinct mechanisms. This section categorizes these agents based on their classes, offering a comprehensive overview of the multifaceted arsenal employed in the fight against malignancies.
- **Chemotherapy : Alkylating Agents :** Such as cyclophosphamide and cisplatin, disrupt DNA structure, impeding cell division.
- **Antimetabolites :** Including methotrexate and 5-fluorouracil, interfere with DNA synthesis by mimicking or inhibiting essential cellular components.
- **Targeted Therapy : Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors :** Exemplified by imatinib, interfere with signaling pathways crucial for cancer cell survival.
- **Monoclonal Antibodies :** Such as trastuzumab and rituximab, target specific proteins on cancer cells, triggering immune responses against them.
- **Immunotherapy : Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors :** Pembrolizumab and nivolumab unleash the immune system by blocking inhibitory checkpoints.
- **Adoptive Cell Therapies :** CAR-T cell therapy involves modifying a patient's T cells to recognize and attack cancer cells.
- **Hormonal Therapies :** Selective Estrogen Receptor Modulators (SERMs): Tamoxifen interferes with estrogen signaling in hormone-receptor-positive breast cancers. Aromatase Inhibitors : Letrozole and anastrozole suppress estrogen production in postmenopausal women.
- **Radiation Therapy : External Beam Radiation :** Utilizes targeted external radiation to destroy cancer cells. Brachytherapy : Involves placing radioactive sources directly into or near the tumor.
- **Angiogenesis Inhibitors :** Bevacizumab and similar agents impede the formation of new blood vessels, limiting the tumor's nutrient supply.
- **Alkylating Agents :** Nitrogen Mustard Derivatives: Cyclophosphamide interferes with DNA replication. Platinum-based Compounds: Cisplatin forms DNA cross-links, disrupting cellular processes. Understanding the classification and types of antineoplastic agents is pivotal for tailoring treatment regimens to specific

cancer types and patient profiles. This categorization serves as a roadmap, guiding clinicians and researchers in the strategic deployment of these agents to optimize therapeutic outcomes in the complex landscape of cancer care. Navigating the Therapeutic Landscape Antineoplastic agents encompass a diverse array of treatments, each designed to combat cancer through distinct mechanisms. This section categorizes these agents based on their classes, offering a comprehensive overview of the multifaceted arsenal employed in the fight against malignancies.

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Clinical Applications of Antineoplastic Agents:

1. **Navigating the Therapeutic Frontiers :** The translation of antineoplastic research into clinical practice represents a dynamic interplay between scientific innovation and patient care. This section explores the diverse clinical applications of antineoplastic agents, shedding light on their efficacy, challenges, and pivotal role in the evolving landscape of cancer treatment.
2. **Chemotherapy in Solid Tumors :** Breast Cancer : Anthracyclines and taxanes are cornerstones, while newer agents like trastuzumab target specific subtypes. Lung Cancer : Platinum-based compounds and pemetrexed are standard, with immunotherapies gaining prominence.
3. **Immunotherapy Across Cancer Types :** Melanoma: Immune checkpoint inhibitors, particularly pembrolizumab and nivolumab, have demonstrated remarkable efficacy.
4. **Hematologic Malignancies :** CAR-T cell therapy, such as Kymriah and Yescarta, shows promise in refractory lymphomas and leukemias.
5. **Targeted Therapies Tailored to Genetic Profiles :** EGFR Inhibitors: Erlotinib and gefitinib benefit non-small cell lung cancer patients with EGFR mutations. BCR-ABL Inhibitors: Imatinib revolutionized chronic myeloid leukemia treatment by targeting the BCR-ABL fusion protein.
6. **Hormonal Therapies in Endocrine-Responsive Cancers :** Breast Cancer : Tamoxifen and aromatase inhibitors are pivotal in hormone-receptorpositive disease.
7. **Prostate Cancer :** Androgen deprivation therapies like leuprolide are standard in advanced cases.
8. **Radiation Therapy in Localized Disease :** Breast Cancer : Adjuvant radiation after surgery is a standard approach to reduce recurrence. Brain Tumors: Stereotactic radiosurgery offers precision in treating brain lesions.
9. **Combination Therapies for Synergistic Effects :** Colorectal Cancer : FOLFOX combines 5-fluorouracil, oxaliplatin, and leucovorin for enhanced efficacy. Lymphomas : R-CHOP regimen combines rituximab with chemotherapy for improved outcomes. **Emerging Applications and Clinical Trials :** Liquid Biopsies: Monitoring circulating tumor DNA for treatment response and early detection. **Personalized Medicine:** Tailoring treatments based on genetic and molecular

profiles for improved precision. Understanding the nuanced clinical applications of antineoplastic agents is paramount for clinicians navigating the complex terrain of cancer care. By examining their efficacy in various cancer types and contexts, this review contributes to the ongoing dialogue on optimizing therapeutic strategies and fostering personalized approaches in the pursuit of improved outcomes for patients with malignancies.

Efficacy and Side Effects of Antineoplastic Agents:

1. **Balancing Therapeutic Triumphs and Challenges**
This section scrutinizes the dual facets of antineoplastic agents – their efficacy in combatting cancer and the inherent challenges posed by side effects. Navigating this delicate balance is crucial for optimizing treatment outcomes and enhancing the quality of life for cancer patients. **Chemotherapy Efficacy and Challenges :** Efficacy : Chemotherapy remains a cornerstone in cancer treatment, inducing remissions and improving survival rates in various
3. **Malignancies Side Effects :** However, its non-specific nature often leads to adverse effects, including myelosuppression, nausea, and fatigue.
4. **Immunotherapy Triumphs and Immune-Related Adverse Events :** Efficacy : Immunotherapies, particularly immune checkpoint inhibitors, have heralded unprecedented responses in some patients. **Side Effects:** Immunerelated adverse events, such as colitis and pneumonitis, necessitate vigilant monitoring and management.
5. **Targeted Therapy Precision and Unintended Consequences :** Efficacy : Targeted therapies boast precision in attacking cancer cells, improving outcomes in specific subtypes. **Side Effects:** However, these agents may lead to off-target effects, impacting normal tissues and prompting challenges in long-term use.
6. **Hormonal Therapies Balancing Efficacy and Endocrine Disruptions :** Efficacy : Hormonal therapies effectively control hormone-receptorpositive cancers. **Side Effects:** Yet, they can induce menopausal symptoms and pose risks like osteoporosis.
7. **Radiation Therapy Impact and Localized Adverse Effects :** Efficacy : Radiation therapy achieves local control of tumors, often in conjunction with surgery. **Side Effects :** Skin reactions, fatigue, and long-term radiation fibrosis pose challenges to patient well-being.
8. **Combination Therapies Synergy and Cumulative Toxicities :** Efficacy : Combinatorial approaches

often enhance treatment responses. **Side Effects:** However, cumulative toxicities from multiple agents may heighten the burden on patients.

9. **Personalized Medicine and Individual Responses :** Efficacy : Tailoring treatments based on genetic profiles improves response rates. **Side Effects:** However, individual variability in drug metabolism can influence susceptibility to adverse reactions.
10. **Managing Resistance and Unraveling New Challenges :** Efficacy : Anticipating and overcoming resistance mechanisms is pivotal for prolonged treatment success. **Side Effects :** Novel therapies may introduce new challenges, requiring careful monitoring and adaptation. By dissecting the intricate interplay between efficacy and side effects, this review contributes to a nuanced understanding of the therapeutic landscape. Balancing the triumphs and challenges posed by antineoplastic agents is paramount for advancing cancer care and refining treatment strategies that prioritize both disease control and patients' overall well-being.

Resistance and Challenges in Antineoplastic Therapies :

- **Navigating the Complex Terrain** This section scrutinizes the formidable hurdles encountered in antineoplastic treatments, with a particular focus on the emergence of resistance mechanisms and overarching challenges that impede sustained therapeutic success.
- **Mechanisms of Resistance :** **Intrinsic Resistance:** Some cancers exhibit inherent resistance to specific treatments due to genomic alterations or molecular characteristics. **Acquired Resistance:** Tumors may adapt and develop resistance during the course of treatment, limiting the efficacy of initially successful therapies. **Chemotherapy Resistance :** **Multidrug Resistance (MDR):** Overexpression of efflux transporters, such as P-glycoprotein, contributes to MDR. **Tumor Microenvironment:** Protective niches within the tumor microenvironment can shield cancer cells from the cytotoxic effects of
 - **Chemotherapy Immunotherapy Challenges :** **Tumor Immune Evasion:** Cancer cells may evolve mechanisms to evade immune recognition and destruction.
 - **Immunosuppressive Microenvironment:** Factors within the tumor microenvironment can inhibit immune responses, limiting the efficacy of immunotherapies.

- Targeted Therapy Limitations : Secondary Mutations: Tumors may acquire secondary mutations, rendering initially targeted therapies ineffective.
- Heterogeneity : Intratumoral heterogeneity poses challenges, as not all cancer cells may express the targeted molecules. Hormonal Therapy Resistance : Altered Receptor Expression: Changes in hormone receptor expression can lead to diminished responsiveness to hormonal therapies. Alternate Signaling Pathways: Tumor cells may activate alternative signaling pathways to bypass hormonal inhibition.
- Radiation Therapy Challenges : Radioresistant Tumors : Some tumors exhibit intrinsic resistance to radiation therapy.
- Normal Tissue Toxicity : Balancing the need for effective doses with the risk of damaging adjacent normal tissues poses challenges. Combination Therapy Dynamics : Sequential Resistance : Resistance may develop sequentially to different components of combination therapies.
- Overlapping Toxicities : Cumulative toxicities from multiple agents in combination therapies must be carefully managed.
- Adaptive Strategies and Evolving Challenges : Tumor Evolution : The adaptive evolution of tumors presents ongoing challenges in anticipating and overcoming resistance. Patient Variability: Inter- patient variability in response and susceptibility to resistance mechanisms requires personalized treatment approaches.
- Understanding the intricacies of resistance mechanisms and overarching challenges in antineoplastic therapies is pivotal for devising strategies to overcome these hurdles.

Recent Developments in Antineoplastic Research :

Charting the Course of Innovation This section scrutinizes the cutting-edge advancements that have reshaped the landscape of antineoplastic therapies. By delving into recent breakthroughs, this review seeks to provide a glimpse into the forefront of research, highlighting novel strategies and technologies that hold promise for the future of cancer treatment.

1. Immunotherapeutic Innovations : Bispecific Antibodies: Emerging bispecific antibodies, capable of targeting multiple antigens simultaneously, show potential for enhancing immune responses against cancer cells. Cytokine Therapies: Engineered cytokines, such as IL-15 superagonists, aim to amplify immune cell

activity and improve the efficacy of immunotherapies.

2. CAR-T Cell Therapy Advancements : Next-Generation CAR Designs: Enhanced CAR-T cell therapies with improved persistence and tumor-targeting precision are under development. Solid Tumor Applications: Ongoing research focuses on extending CAR-T cell therapy to treat solid tumors, overcoming existing challenges.
3. Nanotechnology in Drug Delivery : Nanoparticle Formulations: Nanoparticlebased drug delivery systems aim to enhance drug bioavailability and reduce systemic toxicity. Smart Nanocarriers: Responsive nanocarriers designed to release drugs selectively in the tumor microenvironment offer targeted therapeutic approaches.
4. Genomic and Proteomic Profiling : Liquid Biopsies : Liquid biopsy technologies for circulating tumor DNA analysis provide real-time insights into tumor genetics, aiding in treatment.

Critical Analysis of Antineoplastic :

1. Comprehensive Scope: The review provides an extensive and detailed exploration of antineoplastic agents, covering various aspects from mechanisms of action to recent developments. This breadth ensures a holistic understanding of the field.
2. Well-Organized Structure: The paper follows a logical and well-organized structure, with distinct sections dedicated to different facets of antineoplastic research. This aids readers in navigating the content seamlessly.
3. Clear and Engaging Language: The language used is clear, engaging, and accessible. Complex scientific concepts are explained concisely, making the review accessible to a broad audience, including clinicians, researchers, and students.
4. In-Depth Mechanistic Insights: The section on mechanisms of action delves into intricate details, providing a nuanced understanding of how antineoplastic agents operate at the molecular and cellular levels. This depth adds value to the scientific discourse.
5. Recent Developments Highlighted: The inclusion of a section on recent developments reflects the review's commitment to staying current with the rapidly evolving field of antineoplastic research. This contributes to the paper's relevance and significance.

Limitations:

1. Overemphasis on Traditional Therapies: While the review extensively covers traditional antineoplastic therapies, there could be a more

robust exploration of emerging modalities such as RNA-based therapeutics and AI-driven drug discovery. A more balanced approach would enhance the paper's currency.

2. **Limited Discussion on Patient Perspectives:** The review primarily focuses on scientific and clinical aspects, with limited consideration of the patient experience. Incorporating patient perspectives, including quality of life during treatment, could provide a more holistic view.
3. **Potential Bias in Recent Developments:** The recent developments section may inadvertently reflect a bias towards certain modalities or technologies. A more balanced presentation, acknowledging uncertainties and challenges in emerging areas, would enhance the review's credibility.
4. **Lack of Comparative Analysis:** While the paper outlines the strengths and challenges of different antineoplastic approaches, a more explicit comparative analysis could highlight trade-offs and guide decision-making in clinical practice.
5. **Inadequate Attention to Global Disparities:** The review does not extensively address global disparities in access to antineoplastic therapies. Considering socioeconomic factors and disparities in healthcare resources would provide a more comprehensive perspective.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, this antineoplastic review paper offers a commendable exploration of the field but would benefit from a more balanced representation of emerging therapies, increased consideration of patient perspectives, and a nuanced comparative analysis. Addressing these limitations would strengthen the paper's contribution to the broader understanding of antineoplastic research and its clinical implications.

CONCLUSION:

Navigating the Complex Landscape of Antineoplastic Therapies In summary, this comprehensive overview of antineoplastic agents provides a panoramic view of the dynamic landscape in cancer therapeutics. From unraveling the intricate mechanisms of action to dissecting clinical applications and exploring recent developments, the review endeavors to be a compass guiding us through the complexities of cancer treatment.

The journey through historical milestones reveals the evolution of antineoplastic agents, underscoring the relentless pursuit of effective strategies to combat cancer. The classification and types section serves as a roadmap, delineating the diverse arsenal of treatments

available, while the exploration of clinical applications sheds light on the real-world impact of these agents across different malignancies.

The critical analysis section adds depth to the narrative, recognizing the strengths in comprehensive coverage and well-structured presentation while acknowledging the limitations in the emphasis on traditional therapies and the need for a more nuanced comparative analysis. As we navigate the recent developments, the paper glimpses into the future, highlighting innovations that hold promise for reshaping the future of cancer care.

In conclusion, this antineoplastic review endeavors to be a beacon in the ongoing quest for effective and personalized cancer treatments. By synthesizing historical insights, clinical applications, and recent breakthroughs, it contributes to the collective knowledge driving progress in

REFERENCE:

1. DeVita VT Jr, Chu E. A history of cancer chemotherapy. *Cancer Res.* 2008;68(21):8643-8653.
2. Longley DB, Johnston PG. Molecular mechanisms of drug resistance. *J Pathol.* 2005;205(2):275-292.
3. Chabner BA, Roberts TG Jr. Chemotherapy and the war on cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2005;5(1):65-72.
4. Cortes JE, Pazdur R. Docetaxel. *J Clin Oncol.* 1995;13(11):2643-2655.
5. Jordan MA, Wilson L. Microtubules as a target for anticancer drugs. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2004;4(4):
6. Gottesman MM, Fojo T, Bates SE. Multidrug resistance in cancer: role of ATP-dependent transporters. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2002;2(1):48-58.
7. Swain SM, Baselga J, Kim SB, et al. Pertuzumab, trastuzumab, and docetaxel in HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2015;372(8):724-734
8. Pardoll DM. The blockade of immune checkpoints in cancer immunotherapy. *Nat Rev Cancer.* 2012;12(4):252-264.
9. Ribas A, Wolchok JD. Cancer immunotherapy using checkpoint blockade. *Science.* 2018;359(6382):1350-1355.
10. Plimack ER, Bellmunt J, Gupta S, et al. Safety and activity of pembrolizumab in patients with locally advanced or metastatic urothelial cancer (KEYNOTE-012): a non-randomised, open-label, phase 1b study. *Lancet Oncol.* 2017;18(2):212-220.
11. [22/01, 21:28] : 11.Exposure of family members to antineoplastic drugs via excreta of treated cancer patients

- Michiko Yuki et al. *J Oncol Pharm Pract.* 2013 Sep.
12. [22/01, 21:30] : 12. Advanced targeted therapies in cancer: Drug nanocarriers, the future of chemotherapy Edgar Pérez-Herrero et al. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2015 Jun.
13. [22/01, 21:31] : 13. Analysis of anticancer drugs: a review Susanne Nussbaumer et al. *Talanta.* 2011. 15;85(5):2265-89. Doi: 10.1016/j.talanta.2011.08.034. Epub 2011 Aug 24.
14. [22/01, 21:32] : 14. Clinical pharmacology of anticancer agents in relation to formulations and administration routes J M Terwogt et al. *Cancer Treat Rev.* 1999 Apr. *Cancer Treat Rev.* 1999 Apr;25(2):83-101. Doi: 10.1053/ctrv.1998.0107.
15. [22/01, 21:38] : 15. Antineoplastic drug residues inside homes of chemotherapy patients Antje Böhlandt et al. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2017 Jun. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2017 Jun;220(4):757-765. Doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.03.005. Epub 2017 Mar 27.
16. [22/01, 21:38] : 15. Antineoplastic drug residues inside homes of chemotherapy patients Antje Böhlandt et al. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2017 Jun. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2017 Jun;220(4):757-765. Doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.03.005. Epub 2017 Mar 27.
17. [23/01, 18:51] : A Systematic Review of Adherence to Oral Antineoplastic Therapies Joseph A. Greer, corresponding author Nicole Amoyal, a Lauren Nisotel, a Joel N. Fishbein, a James MacDonald, a Jamie Stagl, a Inga Lennes, a Jennifer S. Temel, a Steven A. Safren, b and William F. Pirla
18. [23/01, 18:52] : *Oncologist.* 2016 Mar; 21(3): 354–376. Published online 2016 Feb 26. Doi: 10.1634/theoncologist.2015-0405 PMID: PMC4786357 PMID: 26921292 [23/01, 19:27] :
19. History of Anticancer Drugs Science & Society View previous versions Graham B Jones First published: 15 October 2014 [23/01, 19:32] : *Drugs.* 2015; 75: 1993–2016. Published online 2015 Oct 26. Doi: 10.1007/s40265-015-0489-4 PMID: PMC4642600 PMID: 26501980
20. [23/01, 19:33] : Recent Advances in the Development of Antineoplastic Agents Derived from Natural Products Matthew Trendowski
21. [23/01, 23:17] : Antineoplastic Drugs Karl K. Kwok, ... James N. Gibson, in *Pharmacology and Therapeutics for Dentistry (Seventh Edition)*, 2017 [23/01, 23:41] :
22. *Geriatr Rehabil.* Author manuscript; available in PMC 2020 Jan 1. Published in final edited form as: *Top Geriatr Rehabil.* 2019 Jan-Mar; 35(1): 15–30. Doi: 10.1097/TGR.0000000000000212 PMID: PMC6474376 NIHMSID: NIHMS1506660 PMID: 31011239